

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SAN FRANCISCO DISTRICT: INPUTS TO PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT GUIDELINES

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Parental Involvement on Academic Performance of San Francisco District: Inputs to Parental Engagement Guidelines

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Abstract

Parents inevitable role in nurturing their child does not end at home. It extends its care and involvement towards their child's schooling. The involvement of parents in academic performance of their child. The study aims to know the correlation of parental involvement and academic performance of Grade 6 learners in San Francisco District and make a guideline that will help in parental engagement. Using descriptive-correlational research design approach that utilizes survey questionnaire to gather numerical data, the researcher compared the academic performance and the student's perception on parental involvement with a ten item questionnaire focusing on Epstein Theory of Parental Involvement such as parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision- making and collaborating with the community. With 140 sample population the results showed that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance to parental involvement but there is a significant relationship with regards to the parent-child relationship and parental involvement. Thus, the implication of this study could be used to promote and help parents through creating guidelines to parental engagement.

Keywords: *academic performance, learning at home, parenting, parental involvement, volunteering*

Introduction

Parents are the first teachers of the child. Parents have to work really hard with their own personal development if they are going to help and motivate their child to rise to the bar of excellence. In this regard, research has shown a link between children's academic achievement and parental involvement (MARTIN, 2022).

Research has demonstrated that parental engagement in a child's education yields a favorable influence on their academic performance. It also increases the chances of kids being engaged and motivated in school, leading to greater academic success. Parental participation is a significant determinant that has a pivotal impact on a child's academic performance (Angwaomaodoko, E. A. 2023). Parents are regarded as one of the major factors influencing a child's academic success (Smith and Sheridan, 2019). Parents is another important element in a child's development is their parents. This is because they have the power and control to raise their kids to be compassionate, motivated, and inspired individuals who actively participate in educational activities. As stated by Ali, et al. (2022), involvement is defined as parents taking an active role in their child's educational endeavours. As a result, they have a big influence on their child's academic development.

Based from the Batas Pambansa The roles, responsibilities, and duties of parents, either individually or collectively, through the systems of the school, in carrying out the national goals for education are outlined in Section 14 of Chapter 232 of the Act, which provides for the establishment and upkeep of an integrated education system in the country. enlisting parents and guardians as partners with the state and schools to improve students' overall wellbeing.

Luna and Del Valle (2023) cited that parents' involvement in their children's education includes what they feel they should be doing. These include activities that benefit a child but call for the parent's presence. The social consensus is that parental involvement has a significant positive impact on academic performance of their children. Similarly, in the study conducted by Ali et. al (2022), revealed that parent's active involvement in children education may even counterbalance the unfavorable effects of low socio economic status and underprivileged neighborhood. Giving them a strong support to succeed and prosper in life. Furthermore, Naite (2020) discovered that in terms of academic performance and test scores across all disciplines pupils with parents who shown a strong interest in their education outperformed those whose parents showed no interest at all. The results showed that parents should understand the value of supporting and visiting their children at school.

Additionally, Giraldo-Garcia and Roy (2018) cited a research indicating that parental involvement varies across cultures. The relationship between parental involvement and the encouragement of social and emotional learning and skills. Similarly, Tan, Lyu, and Pen (2020) shown that parental participation, irrespective of socioeconomic background, enhances students' achievement. These researchers also reported a positive relationship between parental involvement and student achievement in six areas: parental academic expectations, support of the child's learning, discussions by the parent and child on school-related issues, participation in school governance and events, reading together, and parental emphasis on education.

Furthermore, Abulon (2019) noted that parental involvement strategies were used to entice parents to attend school and participate in the activities of their children. These tactics included screening a movie on specific classroom experiences, showcasing performance-based outputs in different topics on a monthly basis, and offering certificates to the class' top performers at card distribution. The adoption of different tactics led to parents becoming more active in their kids' home and school lives, which inadvertently enhanced

their academic achievement.

However, due to time constraints and issues with the instructional materials, parental involvement can occasionally prevent parents from participating in such educational activities (Tan, Lyu, and Pen, 2020). Similar to this, some parents' involvement in their children's education only serves to demoralize and demotivate their children as a result of their carelessness. This has consequently had a detrimental effect on their successes (Florida and Salac, 2022).

Additionally the Nanay-Teacher Parenting Programme Act, introduced by Congressman Win Gatchalian in 2017 and known in the Philippines as House Bill No. 5243, promotes parental interest in education. "The government's policy is to support and strengthen parents' inherent teaching abilities, enabling them to collaborate with educational institutions by facilitating and advancing learning at home, with the goal of raising their children to become the responsible, competent, patriotic, and morally upright leaders of the future," claims Gatchalian. In order for children to have a strong support system for their parents and guardians, this programme teaches every parent to be a daughter or son's mentor. This government action could improve the bond between parents and children and have a general positive impact on children's behaviour.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the parental involvement on academic performance of San Francisco District. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perception of their parent-child relationship?
2. What is the respondents perceive level of involvement of their parent, in terms of:
 - 2.1. parenting;
 - 2.2. communicating;
 - 2.3. volunteering;
 - 2.4. learning at home;
 - 2.5. decision making; and
 - 2.6. collaborating with the community?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondent in the first quarter of the academic year 2023-2024?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' perception of the parent-child relationship and parental involvement?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of parental involvement and academic performance of the learners?
6. What guidelines for parental engagement can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

Based on the issue's applicability, the researcher used a survey technique to implement the descriptive research approach. The goal of descriptive research methodology was to produce accurate and methodical descriptions of a population, circumstance, or phenomenon. When identifying characteristics, frequencies, trends, and classifications is the aim of the research, this is an appropriate choice (McCombes, 2019). The descriptive research design in this study was best suited to get the correlational of academic performance and perception of child's in parental involvement.

Respondents

This study utilized the students from Grade 6 who were enrolled in the School Year at San Francisco District, which was located at San Pablo City, were the subject of the study and selected. They were chosen because Grade 6 students have the ability to answer on their own and enough critical thinking to analyse and understand the survey questions. They also were also chosen for they are transitioning from elementary to junior high school. Thus, the researcher wants to find out if there were effects on parental involvement given to them.

The parents of the respondents granted permission for their children to participate. The researcher purposively selects the District of San Francisco because it is where she teaches.

This study opted to use a complete enumeration sampling method because of its limited population. A complete enumeration sampling is a technique employed in surveys and data analysis to thoroughly evaluate every conceivable element within a limited collection. The process entails choosing, obtaining, and measuring a portion of the population, with the objective of obtaining a representative sample that meets particular criteria. This is especially advantageous when working with limited sample sizes, since it enables the execution of a precise test by taking into account the entire distribution of the test statistic information is collected from each and every member of the population through questionnaire.

Instrument

This study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire from Luna (2023) which covered parental involvement and learners' perception on

parent-child relationship. This instrument was composed of two parts; the first part was the perception of parent-child relationship and the second part as the perception of the respondents on parental involvement in school under 6 categories; parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making and collaborating with the community.

The first part of the questionnaire contained the data privacy clause, approval and consent letters for the respondents' information and the academic grade of the learners for the first quarter in the school year 2023-2024.

The second part of the questionnaire will contain the 4-point Likert scale on the perception of parent-child relationship with ten questions while the last part was the perception of of the parental involvement in school involving the six categories of Epstein Theory of Parental Involvement.

Procedure

The data from this study was collected on November 2023-February 2024. The researcher followed a standard procedure in conducting the data gathering. First, the researcher made a letter seeking the approval for the conduct of study gathering to the OIC- Schools Division Superintendent and Public Schools District Supervisor of San Francisco District, together with the research questionnaire, then, granted a permission to undertake the study. After that, letters were also given to the school principals for the permission to conduct the study. Prior to administering the questionnaire, the researcher ensured that the parents of the respondents received an orientation and provide their consent. Upon receiving consent from the principal to proceed with the study, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire during the parent's orientation. The survey conducted throughout a span of seven days. Data gathered from the respondents during their post-class hours. Upon gathering all the questionnaires, the results were tabulated, compiled, treated, and interpreted. Every participant in the program received a numerical representation for personal privacy. The student code was unchanged for the full research project.

The information gathered for this study was arranged into tables, and the questionnaire responses were used to determine the average score. This involved the following statistical analysis: frequency count and percentage, in order to gauge the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils with respect to their first assessment test given in the first quarter.

The respondents' opinions of the parent-child bond and their parents' engagement in different facets of parenting were evaluated using the mean and standard deviation.

The relationship between the learner's evaluation of the parent-child relationship and parental participation was examined using the Spearman Rho- Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho). The association between students' academic performance in English and their opinions on parent-child interactions and parental participation was examined using the same statistical method.

The researcher used a variety of electronic sources, journals, publications, and some related studies to gather data for the study.

Data Analysis

This study used both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Descriptive statistics in the form of mean and standard deviation was used to determine the perception of the respondents on parent-child relationship. The same treatment was also used to determine the perceived level of involvement of the parents in terms of parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making and collaborating with the community. The first quarter's academic performance of the respondents was assessed using Frequency Count and Percentage.

Likewise, the association between parental participation and the perspective of the parent-child connection was examined using Spearman Rho.

The association between academic achievement and the perceived degree of parental participation was also examined using it.

A correlation strength guideline was utilized to examine the link between a learner's perspective of the parent-child relationship and parental participation. Similarly, the correlation between a learner's academic performance, their opinions on parent-child relationships, and parental participation was analyzed using the same criteria for measuring the strength of association. The Spearman Rho correlation coefficient (r) was used to analyzed the association between the learner's view of the parent-child relationship and parental participation. The same method of statistics was involved in understanding how students' academic achievement was related to their views about the parental-child relationship and level of parent involvement.

Ethical Considerations

The Vice President for Research and Innovation and the University President approved the study's conduct and gave their blessing. It was approved and sent to the Vice President for Academic Affairs, who will distribute it and forward it to the college deans, program chairs, and students who participated in the survey as respondents.

Prior to the research instrument being administered, the respondents were informed about the data privacy clause and signed an informed consent form, which was approved by the University Data Privacy Officer and the Intellectual Property Rights Head of the Vice President for Research and Innovation. In addition, the researcher follows the National Ethical Guidelines involving human

respondents securing parental consent. The respondents were also given this information when completing the questionnaire.

Results and Discussion

This section provides the study's results, analysis, interpretation of the collected data, and the statistical treatment employed in this study.

Table 1. *Perception of the Respondents on Parent-Child Relationship*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
My parents impart religious beliefs and values to me.		
1 (Tinuturuan ako ng aking mga magulang pananampalataya at mga kaugalian)	3.61	Strongly Agree
My parents allow me to express my feelings and opinions		
2 (Hinahayaan ako ng aking mga magulang na ipahayag ang aking mga saloobin at opinyon)	3.11	Agree
My parents allow me to solve problems on my own.		
3 (Hinahayaan ako ng aking mga magulang sa solusyunan ang aking mga problema na may tamang gabay)	3.24	Agree
4 I always respect my parents (Iginagalang ko ang aking mga magulang sa lahat ng oras)	3.72	Strongly Agree
My parents discipline me for my misconduct		
5 (Dinidisciplina ako ng aking mga magulang upang itama ang mga maling gawain)	3.71	Strongly Agree
I always obey my parents' rules with respect		
6 (Sinusunod ko ang aking mga magulang na may paggalang)	3.64	Strongly Agree
My parents provide basic needs for our family		
7 (Ang aking mga magulang ang nagbibigay ng mga pangunahing pangangailangan ng pamilya)	3.65	Strongly Agree
My parents taught me the foundation for success		
8 (Itinuturo ng aking mga magulang ang paraan upang maging matagumpay sa buhay)	3.48	Strongly Agree
My parents express their love and concern for me		
9 (Inihahayag ng aking mga magulang ang kanilang pagmamahal at pagmamalasakit sa akin)	3.63	Strongly Agree
My parents are the most important people in my life		
10 (Ang aking mga magulang ang pinakamahalagang tao sa aking buhay)	3.77	Strongly Agree
Total Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.51–3.25, Agree; 1.76–2.50, Disagree; 1.00–1.75, Strongly Disagree.

The data in Table 1 showed the learner's perception of their relationship with parents. A total means of 3.56 and indicated strongly agreement. The indicators that parents impart religious belief and values to students, they always respect their parents, their parents discipline them for misconduct, they always obey their parent's rules with respect, parents provide basic needs for their family, parents taught them the foundation for success, parents express their love and concern for them and parents are the most important people in their life showed strongly agree. With the mean of 3.61, 3.72, 3.71, 3.64, 3.65, 3.48, 3.63, 3.77 respectively.

The findings revealed that all students believed in good parent-child relationships at home. Students know that their parents are doing the right thing for the well-being of the family. Moreover, students have a strong belief that their parents are one of the key driving forces behind maintaining good grades at school.

Additionally, students concur that their parents let them solve difficulties and communicate their thoughts and feelings. Thus, the parents can assist the kids in developing decision-making skills by letting them choose what to dress in and what to play. Because of that, they are likely to boost their confidence levels and develop critical thinking skills. It's all a process for making decisions, and mistakes can be made. Let them learn by their mistakes and do it better next time. Kids that understand this decision-making process are able to learn important life skills that will help them well into adulthood. (Helfand E. 2024). Thus, it implies that students value their parents and look up to them with high respect and authority. This also implies that when the learners pay too much respect to their parents they created a peaceful and harmonious relationships.

Table 2. *Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1 Parenting	3.18	0.68	Moderately Involved
2 Communicating	3.07	0.66	Moderately Involved
3 Volunteering	2.86	0.73	Moderately Involved
4 Learning At Home	3.31	0.66	Highly Involved
5 Decision- Making	3.11	0.64	Moderately Involved
6 Collaborating with community	3.10	0.67	Moderately Involved
Total Mean	3.18	0.68	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

Data in Table 2 showed that the respondents which had a total mean of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.68. The results shown that the perception of the students about their parents' involvement in six categories—parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with the community—reflects a level of mediumness of parental involvement in helping the student to succeed academically by providing every possible help. Young ones believed that parental involvement in their schooling is essential.

Thus, learning at home has the high involvement result from the data. The results broaden our knowledge of parental involvement in education both at home and in schools, as well as the connection between a parent's support of their child and their personal characteristics. (Harpaz, G., Grinshtain Y., Yaffe Y (2024)

Moreover, parental participation is crucial in supporting children from a young age. Parental engagement in their children's education begins with creating a secure and conducive environment at home, offering educational opportunities, providing support, and fostering a positive mindset. Enhancing student academic performance in school through parents' engagement as educational collaborators. The parents' participation is crucial in fostering the advancement of children in areas such as reading, cognition, motivation, and academic success (Anggia et. al, 2020).

The result implied that a strong participation of parents toward school activities and policy will lead to positive academic performance of their child.

Table 3. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Parenting

	Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1	My parents do their work while helping me with my studies and writing. (Tinutulungan ako ng aking mga magulang sa pagbabasa at pagsusulat kahit sila ay may trabaho.)	3.14	0.91	Moderately Involved
2	My parents and I watch movies together to enhance my vocabulary. (Sinasamahan ako ng aking mga magulang na manood ng movies upang lumawak ang aking bokabularyo.)	2.81	0.99	Moderately Involved
3	My parents help me to improve my skills. (Tinutulungan ako ng aking mga magulang upang madagdagan ang aking kasanayan.)	3.41	0.79	Highly Involved
4	My parents praised me for my effort and good attitude. (Pinupuri ako ng aking mga magulang sa aking pagsisikap at magandang pag-uugali.)	3.32	0.88	Highly Involved
5	My parents talk to me to develop my vocabulary. (Kinakausap ako ng aking mga magulang upang mapalawak pa ang aking bokabularyo.)	3.22	0.81	Moderately Involved
Total Mean		3.18	0.68	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

According to the respondents' perceptions, the data in Table 3 demonstrated a moderate level of involvement in parenting. Based on a mean score of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.68, students' perception that their parents raised them as children indicates considerable participation. The findings show that there is still a discernible amount of parental connection with their child even when parents are preoccupied with their own obligations.

In addition, to maintain these strong bonds, it was important to maintain open communication channels, demonstrate authoritative parenting, and communicate pride in non-academic qualities (Jacobs and Carmelita, 2023).

Moreover, the Parenting for Lifelong Health offers free, open-source, playful parenting materials based on evidence both during and following the COVID-19 pandemic. Resources specially developed to enhance the quality of relationships between parents and children and to decrease violence towards children include how to teach via play, handle challenging and rewarding behaviors, create structure and routines in the home, discuss COVID-19, keep kids safe online, and decrease stress and conflict (COVID-19: 24/7 PARENTING n.d).

Furthermore, many parents today attempt to control and monitor the amount of time their kids spend on screens because they are genuinely concerned for the well-being of their kids. Our research sounds a call: parents should not only help their children navigate their digital lives but also learn to manage their own. Moved by such worries, some parents go so far as to take courses or even hire "digital parenting" coaches (Kostadin an Dunn, 2019).

On the other hand, in the research of Gilmour (2023) reveals that the parenting mindset has shifted from "do as I do" to "fix what we did." An entire generation of millennials is coming at parenting with the level of preparation, purpose, and professionalism they would invest in their next move professionally.

Thus, this implies that when parents were involved in honing their child's skills and praised them with their efforts and good attitude students will able to have a good outcome with their performance.

Table 4. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Communicating

	Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1	My parents communicate with my teacher. (Nakikipag-ugnayan ang aking mga magulang sa aking guro).	3.21	0.89	Moderately Involved
2	My parents communicate with my teacher regarding my academic progress. (Nakikipag-ugnayan ang aking mga magulang sa aking guro upang alamin ang pag-unlad ko)	3.21	0.81	Moderately Involved
3	My parents give positive feedback about classroom activities, school programs, and events. (Positibong nagbibigay-puna ang aking mga magulang sa gawaing pansilid, programang pampaaralan gayundin sa mga aktibidad)	3.11	0.91	Moderately Involved
4	My parents are interested to get involved in different activities in school. (Masiglang nakikilahok ang aking mga magulang sa mga programa ng paaralan)	2.90	0.99	Moderately Involved
5	My parents help my teacher in encouraging me to work independently with my subject. (Katulong ng guro ang aking mga magulang na mahikayat akong gawing mag-isa ang mga aralin sa subjek)	2.94	0.91	Moderately Involved
Total Mean		3.07	0.66	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

The data in Table 4 showed the perception of the students on the involvement of their parents in terms of communicating. It indicated that there is a moderate involvement of parents based on a mean of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.66. The respondents reported that parents are moderately involved in communicating with teachers about school projects and progress. Parents also provide positive feedback on classroom activities, school programs, and events, with a mean of 3.11 and a standard deviation of 0.91. Parents are perceived to be moderately involved in school activities. Learners believe their parents are moderately involved in encouraging them to work independently.

This implies that if there is an open communication between parents and faculty members and administration it will have an easy way of giving information and direction to authorities.

Table 5. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Volunteering

	Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1	My parents serve as active members in school Organization. (Aktibong miyembro ng school Organization ang aking mga magulang.)	2.57	1.05	Moderately Involved
2	My parents support other school activities. (Sinusuportahan ng aking mga magulang ang iba't ibang programa ng paaralan.)	2.99	0.86	Moderately Involved
3	My parents encourage other parents to join the organization and other related activities in school. (Hinihikayat ng aking mga magulang ang kapwa niya magulang na sumali sa Club Organization maging sa iba pang programa na nauugnay rito.)	2.74	0.96	Moderately Involved
4	My parents volunteer to give an inspirational message. (Boluntaryong nagbibigay ng madamdaming mensahe ang aking mga magulang.)	2.88	0.95	Moderately Involved
5	My parents support school activities. (Sinusuportahan ng aking mga magulang ang mga gawain sa paaralan)	3.14	0.92	Moderately Involved
Total Mean		2.86	0.73	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

Data in Table 5 showed parental involvement in terms of volunteering, indicated a total mean of 2.86 as well as standard deviation of 0.73 which showed that parents were moderately involved in volunteering in school activities related to volunteering. The results of serving as an active member of organization, encouraging other parents to be part of the organization, and volunteering to give inspirational messages were interpreted as moderately involved. While many parents are engaged in their child's education, most of them lack the time to volunteer for school events. Primarily due to their occupations. All indications suggest that parents are somewhat involved in supporting school activities, as seen by the pupils.

In addition to supporting their child at home, parents who desire to feel engaged in their child's life will want to volunteer or serve at the school. Urhahne (2019) draws attention to the reality that parents will approach assisting their children differently than teachers do youngster succeeds. Parents can get involved by lending a hand at the school bookfair, helping a kid with their arithmetic homework, or reading to them. But occasionally, parents' ability to assist at the school may be restricted (Rattenborg et al., 2019).

These findings lead into implication that when parents are volunteering to school activities and serve as active member in school organization, support other school activities the performance of their child increases due to the active participation of their child.

Table 6 revealed a high involvement of parents in terms of learning at home ($\bar{X} = 3.31$, $\sigma = 0.66$). Parents encouraging their children to at home frequently resulted in a mean of 3.11 and a standard deviation of 0.92 which was interpreted as moderately involved. Among

the indicators under this variable, only the first indicator was interpreted as moderately involved.

Table 6. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Learning at Home

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1 My parents encourage me to speak at home frequently. (Hinihikayat ako ng aking mga magulang na magsalita palagi sa aming tahanan.)	3.11	0.92	Moderately Involved
2 My parents help me as I struggle with my written homework. (Tinutulungan ako ng aking mga magulang kapag ako ay nahihirapan sa takdang-aralin.)	3.31	0.89	Highly Involved
3 My parents demonstrate a positive attitude towards my studies in learning at home. (Nakikita kong natutuwa ang aking mga magulang na natututo akong sa aming bahay.)	3.41	0.85	Highly Involved
4 My parents encourage me to have a love for reading. (Hinihikayat ako ng aking mga magulang na maging mahilig sa pagbabasa.)	3.34	0.86	Highly Involved
5 My parents make sure that the home environment is welcoming and a motivating place for my study. (Isinasaayos ng aking mga magulang ang aming tahanan sa isang kaaya-aya at tahimik na lugar na magbibigay sigla sa pag-aaral ko.)	3.39	0.81	Highly Involved
Total Mean	3.31	0.66	Highly Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

The students perceived that their parents were actively engaged in assisting them throughout homework difficulties, showcasing the parents' favorable approach towards their academic pursuits. The previous two-five indicators such as my parents help me as I struggle with my written homework, my parents demonstrate a positive attitude towards my studies in learning at home, my parents encourage me to have a love for reading and my parents make sure that the home environment is welcoming and a motivating place for my study suggested a high level of engagement. This study confirms earlier research indicating that parental involvement at home positively affects student academic attainment (Anthony & Ogg, 2019).

In addition, the study of Huang et. al 2022, found that there exist four particular latent class styles which could be used in delineating and naming the ways that parents engage their children in at-home learning. Finding suggests that researchers can deal only with the issues about parenting and the academic achievement of an only child by determining and replicating the parental participation styles at home.

Furthermore, Andy Sapta et. al 2018, mentioned in the study that child's homework is rarely prioritized by parents, thus parents entrust their child's learning at home through tutoring or private tutors.

In line with this, in the study of Liao et.al (2019), parents of elementary school students should make an effort to use proactive and useful techniques to build an equitable and transparent relationship with their kids. As an illustration, treat kids equally when communicating, listen more than you criticize, focus more on life and emotions, acknowledge children's efforts, and downplay the importance of academic achievement. Such a strong parent-child relationship can promote effective communication between parents and children. Children are willing to open up and reveal academic pressure to their parents in order to help them cope with pressure from the outside world, promote the development of their mental health, and prevent the bad feelings and behaviors brought on by academic pressure. They also want their parents to give them constructive criticism and to actively encourage them.

Table 7. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Decision-making

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1 My parents seek advice from the school to attain positive learning outcomes. (Humihingi ng payo ang aking mga magulang sa paaralan upang maging kapakipakinabang ang pagkatuto ko)	2.96	0.91	Moderately Involved
2 My parents provide positive suggestions for learning at home and in school. (Nagbibigay ng magagandang mungkahi ang aking mga magulang sa pagkatuto sa tahanan at sa paaralan.)	3.36	0.81	Highly Involved
3 Parents get involved in decisions concerning a child's academic needs. (Kasama ng paaralan ang aking mga magulang sa pagdedesisyon sa pang-akademikong pangangailangan ng mga mag-aaral.)	2.86	0.94	Moderately Involved
4 My parents attend a quarterly meeting to be updated about my academic progress. (Palagiang dumadalo sa miting ang aking mga magulang upang alamin ang pag-unlad ko.)	3.19	0.89	Moderately Involved
5 My parents are talking to other parents to be updated regarding school issues and concerns learning. (Nakikipag-usap ang aking mga magulang sa kapwa niya magulang upang malaman ang mga bagong isyu at usapin na may kinalaman sa pag-aaral)	3.21	0.89	Moderately Involved
Total Mean	3.11	0.64	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

The results of data in Table 7 presented the respondents' assessment of their parents' engagement in decision-making, indicating moderate participation. The students perceived that their parents were actively engaged in seeking guidance from the school to achieve a favorable learning outcome and offering good suggestions for learning at home and in school. This perception was backed by a mean of 3.11 and a standard deviation of 0.64. Students believed their parents were highly active in decisions regarding their academic needs in the topic, but only moderately interested in attending quarterly meetings. Indicators that parents talking to other parents to be updated regarding school issues and concerns learning showed moderately involved. Furthermore, indicators that parents provide positive suggestions for learning at home and in school showed highly involved. This implies that respondents perceived that their parents care in their well-being both at home and in school. In relation to this, study of Talaid (2018) the most common parenting approach and the best indicator of students' academic success is authoritative.

Table 8. Perception of the Respondents on the Involvement of their Parents in terms of Collaborating with Community

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1 My parents involved themselves in creating the school's localized reading materials found in the community. (Nakikisangkot ang aking mga magulang sa paaralan sa paggawa ng mga panlokal na babasahin na pwedeng matagpuan sa komunidad.)	2.84	0.94	Moderately Involved
2 My parents participate in the school's related activity. (Nakikilahok ang aking mga magulang sa proyektong pampaaralan.)	2.92	0.96	Moderately Involved
3 My parents support project for the learners to develop different skills and communication skills. (Sinusuportahan ng aking mga magulang ang proyektong para sa mga mag-aaral upang mapahusay ang mga kakayahan sa pagsasalita.)	3.16	0.85	Moderately Involved
4 My parents allow me to get involved in school activities that enhance my skills. (Pinapayagan ako ng aking mga magulang na makilahok sa gawaing pampaaralan na magpapaunlad sa kasanayan ko.)	3.48	0.68	Highly Involved
5 My parents collaborate with the school to develop an enhancement program. (Nakikiisa sa paaralan ang aking mga magulang upang makabuo ng programang naglalayong mapaunlad ang pagkatuto ko)	3.11	0.9	Moderately Involved
Total Mean	3.1	0.67	Moderately Involved

Legend: 3.26–4.00, Highly Involved; 2.51–3.25, Moderately Involved; 1.76–2.50, Less Involved; 1.00–1.75, Not Involved.

The findings in Table 8 showed that respondents perceived their parents' involvement in working with the community as moderately involved, with a total mean of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 0.67. The indicators in this table were mostly considered moderately active, except for the fourth indication where parents were extremely involved ($\bar{X}=3.48, \sigma=0.68$). In addition, it was suggested that preparations be made to increase student participation in the classroom and to use modern methods and approaches to increase student engagement in general. (Erdem H. 2024). According to research by Martin (2022) parents can work together to further address their children's academic, social, and emotional needs by obtaining relevant resources and adequate assistance from their community.

Table 9. Academic Performance of the Respondents

First Quarter Average Grade	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
78	2	1.4%	Fairly Satisfactory
79	3	2.1%	Fairly Satisfactory
80	3	2.1%	Satisfactory
81	7	5.0%	Satisfactory
82	13	9.3%	Satisfactory
83	13	9.3%	Satisfactory
84	9	6.4%	Satisfactory
85	13	9.3%	Very Satisfactory
86	11	7.9%	Very Satisfactory
87	17	12.1%	Very Satisfactory
88	8	5.7%	Very Satisfactory
89	11	7.9%	Very Satisfactory
90	15	10.7%	Outstanding
91	8	5.7%	Outstanding
92	4	2.9%	Outstanding
93	2	1.4%	Outstanding
94	1	0.7%	Outstanding
Total	140	100	

Legend: 90–100, Outstanding; 85–89, Very Satisfactory; 80–84, Satisfactory; 75–79, Fairly Satisfactory; below 75, Did Not Meet Expectations.

The results in Table 9 showed the academic performance of Grade 6 students during their First Quarter in school year 2023-2024. The results show that 21.4% were outstanding who got the grade ranges from 90-100 which clearly shows 30 learners have outstanding grade out of 140 respondents. While only 3.5% were interpreted as fairly satisfactory scope from 75-79 correspondingly. The grade ranges from 80 to 84 were 32.1% and interpreted as satisfactory. Furthermore, the grade ranges from 85 to 89 were 42.9% and represented as very satisfactory. It means that many students got the average of very satisfactory. Since 0% of the scores were viewed as falling short of expectations, all of the pupils received grades between 75 and above. Thus, the data that the student got outstanding grades implies the active participation of parents in the child's academic performance.

Table 10. *Correlation of respondents' perception of the parent-child relationship and parental involvement*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Perceived level of Parent-Child Relationship</i>		
Parental Involvement	<i>r – value</i>	Degree of Correlation	<i>ρ – value</i>
Parenting	0.229	Strong relationship	0.631
Communicating	0.229	Strong relationship	0.499
Volunteering	0.229	Strong relationship	0.503
Decision Making	0.229	Strong relationship	0.441
Learning at Home	0.229	Strong relationship	0.556
Collaborating with Community	0.229	Strong relationship	0.527

*Significance value is >0.05

Data shows in Table 10 shows a strong relationship between perceived level of parent-child relationship and parental involvement. In connection to the study of Wen et. al (2024), good adolescent-parent connections, marked by warmth, intimacy, and a suitable ratio of reinforcement to manage behavior, facilitate a smooth transition from childhood to maturity.

In addition, the strong relationship in parenting, communicating, volunteering, decision making, learning at home and collaborating with community showed that parents were hands-on in their child's academic performance.

Table 11. *Correlation the perceived level of parental involvement and academic performance of the learners*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>		
Parental Involvement	Degree of Correlation	<i>ρ – value</i>	
	No or Negligible relationship	0.006	Not significant

*Significance value is >0.05

There is no significant relationship between the level of parent involvement and school achievement perceived by the students. Thus, the data shows that in every one-point increase in parent-child relationship there is 0.229 increase in academic performance of the learner. However, in the study of Boonk L. et. Al (2018), the results of 75 studies examining the relationship between parental involvement and academic success were assessed for this research. Studies carried out between 2003 and 2017 have demonstrated a connection between children's academic success and parental involvement. However, this association is not as strong as historically believed. Correlational research has demonstrated small to medium-sized connections between various parental engagement qualities and academic attainment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

A strong foundation can motivate a youngster to learn even more if parents and kids get along. Academic achievement can be enhanced by parental involvement in six domains: communication, decision-making, parenting, volunteering, at-home learning, and community collaboration. At the 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis that there is no meaningful correlation between students' evaluations of their parent-child connection and their academic success is rejected.

The idea that there is no discernible correlation between learners' perceptions of parental participation and their opinions on the parent-child connection is accepted. The variables don't statistically relate to one another. The hypothesis positing no substantial correlation exists between academic success and learners' perceptions of parental participation.

The following suggestions are given in light of the observations and conclusions:

Parents may have regular communication with their child to monitor their school involvement.

Engage in parenting, volunteering, communicating, decision-making, and collaboration with the community.

Parents must give encouragement and support to child's academic performance.

Parents should make an involvement in their child's educational growth.

Classroom PTA officers may brainstorm on a classroom-based program that will come handy in assisting at-risk learners.

Endorsement of Guideline in Parental Engagement for learner's improvement in learning to school principal for possible implementation in respective grade level.

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